

Pluriliteracies in Higher Education: Developing English competence for interpreters and translators through a deeper learning episode

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Abstract

CLIL practices were widely introduced in Spanish education over twenty years ago (Jover et al., 2024; Otto et al., 2024). Nevertheless, the transition of this methodological innovation to university contexts in Spain seems challenging due to the lack of resources. In this paper, our main aim is to evaluate the potential of applying the principles of CLIL in a university setting, within the framework of a language module through the implementation of a pluriliteracies approach. For that purpose, we present an exploratory didactic proposal in the form of a deeper learning episode for the Language B English 4 (C1) course in a bachelor's degree in Translation and Interpreting at a Spanish online university. While respecting the fundamentals of CLIL, we aim to steer towards pluriliteracies, a more global approach in which learners develop a series of competencies that are key for interpreters and translators. Thus, this project offers a pragmatic example of how a language module can be transformed from a traditional language-led course to a content-based one which is more comprehensive and meaningful. In the learning episode, a series of values, attitudes and key skills such as knowledge and critical understanding begin to emerge (Council of Europe, 2016) through the topic of art and its cultural implications. This, in turn, translates into long-term sustainable curricula aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 4: Quality Education, target 4.7 (United Nations, 2015). Ultimately, this approach could provide language teachers with new opportunities to redefine their role.

Keywords

Deeper Learning; EFL; Pluriliteracies; Sustainable Curricula; Training of Translators and Interpreters.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bilingual school programmes were introduced in the Spanish school system in 2004, almost twenty years ago. This implies the first cohort from those programmes began their university studies in 2016. Despite the variety of models in Spain -18 different ones, according to the Bilingual Education Association¹, and their associated controversies (Anghel et al., 2012; Dobson et al., 2010; Palacios-Hidalgo, 2020), it is undeniable that at its very core lies the objective of improving not only language proficiency but also language education across the different educational levels. It is also indisputable that, in a globalised world, the spread of bilingual programmes is unstoppable.

In terms of university studies, however, advances in bilingual programmes have been more limited (Contero et al., 2018; Lópaz Pérez, 2017; Terrado et al., 2019). Nevertheless, there has been an exponential growth in the number of degrees that can be studied in English at Spanish universities as part of their internationalisation strategies. Whilst school programmes and pre-university teacher training have had Content and Language Integrated Learning (henceforth, CLIL) theories as their focal point, universities seem to have followed English as a Medium of Instruction (henceforth, EMI). The former is defined by Coyle, Hood and Marsh (2010) as,

[...] a dual-focused educational approach in which an additional language is used for the learning and teaching of both content and language. That is, in the teaching and learning process, there is a focus not only on content, and not only on language. Each is interwoven, even if the emphasis is greater on one or the other at a given time. CLIL is not a new form of language education. It is not a new form of subject education. It is an innovative fusion of both. (p. 1)

The latter, on the other hand, is conceptualised as “the use of English language to teach academic subjects [...] where the first language (L1) of the majority of the population is not English” (Dearden, 2014, p. 6). In EMI settings, thus, the focus seems to be on the teachers and their language skills to conduct a lecture in English. In contrast,

¹ <https://www.ebspain.es/>

CLIL is more centred around students' learning experience. Furthermore, CLIL aims to enhance language learning by immersing students in the target language, encouraging interdisciplinary connections between language and content areas, thus promoting a more holistic approach to education. Darn (2006) emphasizes the similarities between CLIL and current models of English Language Teaching (ELT):

A CLIL 'approach' is not far removed from humanistic, communicative and lexical approaches in ELT, and aims to guide language processing and supports language production in the same way that an EFL/ESL course would by teaching techniques for exploiting reading or listening texts and structures for supporting spoken or written language. (p. 4)

The author also advocates for a revision of language education models whose pivotal elements are based on linguistic progression. More recently, Coyle and Meyer's (2021) pluriliteracies approach emphasized the development of multiple literacies beyond traditional reading and writing to enable learners to navigate, communicate, and participate meaningfully in a complex, multicultural, and technologically mediated global society.

Pluriliteracies encompass not only language and textual literacies but also digital, visual, and intercultural literacies. As such, it may open the door for "language teachers to experiment and adapt learning pathways in their classrooms to create their own pluriliteracies environment – which is *not* dependent on other subject disciplines" (p. 144).

Coyle, Halbach, Meyer and Schuck (2018) refer to these models as "language using for learning" (p. 353). Other authors such as Dale (2020) have been working on the reconceptualization of the role of language teachers as subject teachers within the pluriliteracies framework, "applying the pluriliteracies model and genre pedagogies to the teaching of text analysis may offer language teachers a usage-based view of language and provide usage-based pedagogical models for the teaching of their own subject" (p. 160).

Following these tenets, in this article we will explore the possibility of going beyond the traditional schemata of an English course by designing an educational experience that could better fulfil the needs of students in the degree in Translation and Interpreting.

2. CONTEXT

The Valencian International University (henceforth, VIU) is a fully online institution that delivers officially recognised courses at undergraduate and post-graduate levels, including doctoral programmes. The 4-year degree in Translation and Interpreting falls within the scope of the Faculty of Arts, Humanities and Communication.

Lessons at VIU are carried out synchronously, encouraging active participation. Students' involvement is key for the success of the courses, particularly those involving the learning of a foreign language. Students in the degree in Translation and Interpreting must follow the official program, which includes four English subjects which range from B1 to C1 level and have a study load of 6 ECTS each.

The focus of this paper is the subject Language B English 4 (C1 CEFR Level), of which one of the authors is the teacher. The competences and learning outcomes that students must attain at the end of the course are closely related to the Action-Oriented approach (Piccardo & North, 2019) embedded in the vision of the CEFR Companion Volume (2020). In each cohort, there are students who are native or bilingual together with others who are more aligned with the level of the subject in progress. Our challenge is to be able to offer a relevant educational experience in which everyone has an opportunity to learn.

As can be seen in Table 1, complex communicative skills are at the very core of this subject, as well as different textual genres and a variety of application contexts.

Table 1*Language B English 4 Specific Competences (SC) and Learning Outcomes (LO)*

Specific Competences	Learning Outcomes
SC.8. Understand a wide variety of long texts with a certain level of proficiency in Language B, at level C1 of the CEFR.	LR.1. Demonstrate understanding of a wide variety of long texts with a certain level of demand, as well as to recognize implicit meanings in them.
SC.9. Express fluently without much obvious effort to find the appropriate expression in Language B, at level C1 of the CEFR.	LR.2. Express oneself fluently and spontaneously without very evident signs of effort to find the appropriate expression.
SC.10. Use language flexibly for different purposes in Language B at CEFR level C1.	LR.3. Produce clear, well-structured and detailed texts on topics of a certain complexity, showing a correct use of the organizational complexity, showing a correct use of the mechanisms of organization, articulation and cohesion of the text.
SC.11. Produce clear, well-structured and detailed texts on topics of a certain complexity, showing a correct use of language for different complexity, showing a correct use of the mechanisms of organization, articulation and cohesion of the text, in Language B, at level C1 of the CEFR.	
SC.15. Demonstrate skills in linguistic mediation.	

Note. Taken from the official course syllabus, SC and LO are present in the official and accredited curriculum.

Until the academic year 2021-2022, the course material chosen was “Viewpoint”², by Cambridge University Press. Whilst we consider this to be a valid resource, it has proven to be insufficient to address students’ particular needs and enhance students’ motivation due to its focus on a progression based on linguistic features – grammar and vocabulary. On the dedicated website for the book, the authors state that, “each unit consists of four two-page lessons that present grammar, vocabulary, and conversation strategies, and include listening, speaking and reading practice” (para. 2). They also

² <https://www.cambridge.es/en/catalogue/adults/courses/viewpoint/components>

highlight that there is “a ‘Speaking naturally’ activity at the back of the book that presents and practises a feature of pronunciation, linked to the language of the unit” (para. 5). Therefore, the communicative activities proposed in each unit are tailored to the language of the unit, a common occurrence for English teaching materials and course design.

Students have noticed the focus on linguistic aspects in the recurrent student survey that takes place at the end of every course, with negative comments about their learning experience such as:

It [the course] only focuses on grammatical competence, without work on other linguistic skills, such as comprehension and oral expression. There is not any work on the cultural aspects, so necessary for a translator” (Student A, translated from Spanish), or “Only the theoretical materials of Viewpoint [are used], and not many practical activities have been carried out in the classes, everything was practically theory (Student B, translated from Spanish).

Translators and interpreters face great challenges in their work to ensure effective and accurate communication between languages and cultures. Information transfer, pragmatic awareness and conciseness are paramount for their professional success. Consequently, there is a need to provide degree students with opportunities to develop their competences. For that purpose, a Deeper Learning Episode (DLE) was planned following Coyle and Meyer’s (2021) Pluriliteracies Approach to Teaching for Deeper Learning (PTDL).

A DLE transcends the concept of a traditional lesson. It is composed of different outcomes that allow learners and teachers to check that deeper learning is indeed taking place. Deeper Learning is understood as “helping learners ‘connect the dots’ to develop and internalise conceptual knowledge while practising relevant skills and strategies in such a way that they can be successfully transferred to other contexts and problems” (Coyle et al., 2023, p. 1).

At the core of DLEs design are the learners' strengths, needs and interests as well as a realisation of meaning making through Dalton-Puffer's (2013) classification of

cognitive discourse functions, which refer to the various ways in which language is used to convey and manipulate information, thoughts, and ideas in communication. Dalton-Puffer's framework is particularly valuable for understanding how language is used in various contexts and for teaching effective communication skills in different genres of discourse, such as narrative, expository, expressive, and directive. Hence, throughout the DLE students will need to establish relationships between knowledge and communication by engaging in the specific major activity domains integral to the subject (doing, organising, explaining and arguing).

In the following section, the different steps of the planning of a DLE for the Language B English 4 course (C1 CEFR Level) will be presented.

3. DIDACTIC PROPOSAL: EXPLORING PLURILITERACIES THROUGH A DEEPER LEARNING EPISODE ON LINGUISTIC AND INTERCULTURAL MEDIATION

We believe that the transition towards meaningful learning in English language courses in this university degree may involve the implementation of PTDL. Using this approach will enable students to acquire and practise competences that will be useful not only in other academic areas, but also in their future professional lives.

For this reason, in this section, we present the steps that, according to Coyle and Meyer (2021), need to be taken by educational practitioners in order to make the shift towards a more holistic, critical and value-driven teaching-learning process. The focus is therefore on curricular sustainability, i.e. exploring options to promote deeper, significant learning without challenging the specific competences and learning outcomes that are set by the official regulations of the country.

3.1 Essential Steps to Planning a Deeper Learning Episode (DLE)

Coyle and Meyer (2021) propose using five questions “which position educators as designers of learnscapes” (p. 127). These five questions (Q) are key to beginning this transformation towards the planning of a meaningful teaching and learning experience within the pluriliteracies scheme. When designing a DLE, educators need to ask

themselves these fundamental questions. Below, we outline these enquiries in connection with the four dimensions (D) of the PTDL model (Coyle & Meyer, 2017).

- **D1.** Supporting knowledge building (facts, concepts, procedures and strategies).

Q1. What do I want my learners to know or be able to?

While focusing on knowledge (factual, conceptual, procedural, strategic /metacognitive), this question puts the students and their needs at the centre of the learning experience.

- **D2.** Ways of demonstrating understanding (purpose, genre, mode and style).

Q2. How will I know they know?

With different milestones set throughout the DLE, the success of the teaching and learning process can be determined. Through preliminary product outcomes (PPO)(or small preparatory activities that build up on each other) we aim to closely observe learners demonstrate their understanding so that they can perform well when they reach the main product outcome (MPO)(or final task).

- **D3.** Learner-teacher relationships (affect, engagement, mastery, and reflection).

Q3. How can I support active knowledge co-construction for my learners?

It is essential to connect subject-specific ways of constructing and communicating knowledge with learner's strengths, needs and interests to foster learner commitment and achievement. Social-interaction patterns and the use of digital media must be used to support this co-construction of knowledge and learning partnerships.

- **D4.** Ways in which mentoring learning can contribute to learner's growth mindset that directs and sustains their own learning (design, scaffolding, feedback and assessment).

Q4. How will I support my learners every step of the way?

Triggering and increasing student engagement and expertise through relevant topics, dynamic scaffolding, constant feedback, and assessment will help learners achieve the desired competences.

Q5. How will I create and sustain learner engagement?

The answer promotes growth mindsets for deeper learning, where relevance (personal and practical), transfer pathways and critical reflection, revision, and self-improvement are embedded in task design principles.

3.2 A Deeper Learning Episode for Language B English 4

First, in a conceptualising continuum, a DLE follows a logical pathway by focusing on facts in the early stages, then concepts, to finally implementing procedures and strategies. It is, therefore, grounded in the idea that internalisation of conceptual knowledge will only occur when promoting deep understanding, deep practice, and the cultivation of a growth mindset (Coyle & Meyer, 2021).

Secondly, opportunities shall be created for learners to develop the ability to take the content knowledge that was acquired in one setting and apply it to another while expressing understanding in a better and more sophisticated way, taking into account a communicating continuum with a focus on purpose, mode, genre and style (Meyer et al., 2015).

Finally, to make this process meaningful and engaging, the tasks will often involve shared learning and interactions with others as a community, as well as thought-provoking topics through which future translators and interpreters may develop expertise and competences.

The goals of this DLE are, thus, based on a combination of the general competences (GC) of the official Degree in Translation and Interpreting and the specific competences (SC) of the Language B English 4 course:

- GC.1.- **Integrate knowledge** to formulate **judgments** based on information in **3 working languages** (A, B and C) and field of expertise (art), including **reflections on social and ethical responsibilities** in the field of Translation and Interpreting.
- GC.7.- **Collaborate** actively with **other people**, areas and/or organizations in order to achieve common objectives, with the aim of explaining and prevent possible conflicts arising from **cultural differences**.
- SC.8.- Understand a wide **variety** of long **texts** with a certain level of proficiency in Language B, at level C1 of the CEFR.
- SC.10.- **Use language flexibly** for different purposes in Language B at CEFR level C1.
- SC.11.- Produce clear, well-structured and detailed texts on topics of a certain complexity, showing a correct use of language for different complexity, demonstrating a **correct use of the mechanisms** of organization, articulation and cohesion of the text, in Language B, at level C1 of the CEFR.
- SC.15.- Demonstrate skills in linguistic **mediation**.

As a means to integrating these competences, the key elements of the learnscape can be summarised as language proficiency, pluriliteracies, plurilingualism and cultural awareness. The challenge involves envisioning a final task that requires trainees to take these foundations to a practical level. An effective planning technique is to think about the main product outcome first and, from there, plan the episode, taking steps backwards by creating micro tasks which prepare learners (through continuous feedback and revision) to tackle the main assignment.

For the purpose of creating this holistic final task, and keeping the GCs and SCs in mind, the specific questions now become:

- (1) Can we outline a task in which students are able to formulate judgements based on information in three working languages, including reflections on social and ethical responsibilities in the field of translation and interpreting?

- (2) Is it possible for us to build a setting (online) in which the learners are able to work in a collaborative way?
- (3) Could we create the conditions so that the trainees may use a variety of long texts (written, visual, audio, audio-visual) and produce well-structured texts at a C1 level?
- (4) Can we create an outline so that learners are able to demonstrate knowledge, skills and strategies in linguistic and intercultural mediation?

The last big step towards the transformation of the course design also involves integrating the PTDL five guiding questions explored in section 3.1, which will be answered next.

Q1. What do I want my learners to know or be able to?

To answer this enquiry, the contents are selected from the course syllabus and have been re-designed considering Bloom's Taxonomy of thinking skills (Bloom et al., 1956; Anderson et al., 2001).

For promoting a conceptualising and communicating continuum, progression is guaranteed by setting up five different learning stages linked to cognitive discourse functions (CDFs): [1] basic understanding (identify and understand); [2] foundational skills (research, describe, explain, systematise and mediate); [3] deeper understanding (making connections and critical thinking); [4] deep practice (translate, mediate, write) and [5] transfer (apply) as can be seen in Table 2³.

Taking all these notions into account, the final task can then be conceptualised. It consists of a role-play activity in which students work in small groups within a controversial scenario involving a conflict among cultures, which they are challenged to resolve by assuming a particular role. During the learning process, students will have to

³ The planning grid has been dissected into Tables 2-6 so that the questions can be addressed gradually in this text, but it can be found in its entirety in Appendix A (see it [here](#)).

handle a variety of authentic text modalities in different languages and implement cultural, textual and communication mediation techniques.

The Table below shows how the contents evolve in each stage of the episode until they reach the transfer phase, where students are expected to be able to apply what they have learned in this course to other courses in the degree.

Table 2

Designing a Deeper Learning Episode (Q1)

What do I want my learners to know or be able to?
<p>1. Basic understanding:</p> <p>1.1 Identify artistic manifestations by relevant British artists.</p> <p>1.2 Understand the controversies surrounding the world of art.</p> <p>2. Foundational skills:</p> <p>2.1 Do research on the political, environmental and social dimension of art in different languages.</p> <p>2.2 Mediate and organize information.</p> <p>2.3 Describe background and purpose of works of art.</p> <p>2.4 Explain controversial issues surrounding art.</p> <p>2.5 Keep a glossary of terminology to discuss arts.</p> <p>3. Deeper understanding:</p> <p>3.1 Discover the implications of art beyond the visual.</p> <p>4. Deep practice:</p> <p>4.1 Translate & mediate between the Source Text and English (Language B).</p> <p>4.2 Use subject specific language.</p> <p>4.3 Use formal debating code for argumentation.</p> <p>4.4 Write formal texts.</p> <p>5. Transfer:</p> <p>5.1 Focus on specialized translation.</p>

5.2 Debating code and conventions.

5.3 Mediating (cultural & linguistic), Interpreting & Translating - subject specific texts in three working languages.

5.4 Public speaking in English.

5.5 Writing formal texts & APA 7 citation system.

5.6 Global learning dimensions.

Appendix B⁴, section "04 Deep Practice", shows the course materials⁵ that have been conceived for the final product outcome. The first phase of the roleplay entails setting up the context, roles, and purpose of the task. In the second phase, specific information about each interlocutor and links to find useful documents to pursue their goals are provided.

⁴ See Appendix B [here](#).

⁵ The complete teaching materials are available in Appendix B.

Figure 1*DLE Stage 4: Deep practice. Role-play (Phase 2)*

Figure 1 consists of three vertical cards, each with a title, an icon, and a text box. The first card is for a Customs Officer, the second for an Art Manager, and the third for a Mediator. Each card contains specific instructions and context for the role-play activity.

Role	Icon	Text
Customs Officer	Icon of a customs officer in uniform	<p>You are responsible for helping to prevent the importation of illegal and/or dangerous goods including firearms, drugs, alcohol, tobacco and endangered animals into Japan.</p> <p>Due to outbreaks of domestic animal diseases in other countries, most meat and other animal products cannot be brought into Japan. There may be some options to bring animal products into Japan from overseas.</p> <p>Customs Border Japan Embassy of Japan in Australia</p>
Art Manager	Icon of a woman's face	<p>One of your duties as an art manager is to show proper work etiquette and professional approach on all challenges to encourage Damien in new projects that would seem intimidating.</p> <p>You have effective written and verbal communication skills. Your job takes a lot of patience and a sound mind for decision-making.</p> <p>You need to ensure that Damien's art is exhibited at the Tokio Museum, offer enough reasons (examples?) and show willingness to cooperate with the authorities.</p>
Mediator	Icon of three people talking	<p>You are here to facilitate that people find possible solutions to the communication blockage or misunderstanding. The aim is to encourage proposals and solutions.</p> <p>As a cultural and linguistic mediator you have no "power", neither of decision nor of persuasion. Your job is to open channels of communication and help the interlocutors to reach an agreement providing valuable and contrasted information.</p>

Then, fostering a cooperative learning experience, using the Aronson's puzzle technique (Slavin, 1995; García et al., 2012), students will prepare their interventions together with their counterparts. This step will also create a chance for the instructor to give feedback on the students' notes and boost their confidence when they attend the final meeting.

The third phase of the simulation game sets the procedures for the final interaction. The "role-play meeting" worksheet facilitates specific instructions about the duration, dynamics and purpose of the conference. Besides, after the meeting, the group will write a formal letter of request which will need to be submitted together with the meeting recording and minutes. Special attention has been paid to clearly define the guidelines and progression of each activity so as to ensure a more accurate and fairer assessment of all students' submissions by applying the rubrics specifically designed for each task.

Once the content knowledge has been established in the learnscape from least to most cognitively challenging and the final product outcome has been defined, the remaining PTDL questions need to be addressed.

Q2. How will I know they know?

According to Coyle et al. (2023), deeper learning episodes integrate and combine stages of surface learning, consolidation and transfer of knowledge along with their corresponding tasks. This DLE aims to provide a range of opportunities for learners to demonstrate understanding, reflect on their own and their peers' learning progress, revise their work every step of the way using teachers' comments on each milestone and enable better comprehension. This idea connects to the second guiding question, developed in Table 3, which helps us consider the establishment of scaffolding tasks or preliminary product outcomes during the process to ensure effective teacher feedback, formative assessment and deeper learning.

Table 3

Designing a Deeper Learning Episode (Q2)

How will I know they know?
<p>Preliminary product outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Basic understanding</u>. "Controversial works of art": read/listen and summarize information (1.2). ● <u>Foundational skills</u>. "Art. What should we consider?": complete an index card using resources in different languages and modes (2.1-2.4). ● <u>Foundational skills</u>. "Create your own glossary": identify terms, find equivalences and contextualize (2.5). ● <u>Deeper understanding</u>. "Discover the implications of art beyond the visual": open class discussion (3.1). ● <u>Deep Practice</u>. "Role-Play at Narita International Airport": meeting minutes (shared ideas and opinions properly justified with reasons and examples)(4.1-4.4). ● <u>Deep Practice</u>. "Role-Play at Narita International Airport": script produced by groups divided in their different roles (group 1: customs officers; group 2; art managers; group 3: cultural and linguistic mediators). Reviewed by the teacher, but not included in the final mark. ● <u>Deep Practice</u>. "Role-Play at Narita International Airport": formal letter of request (4.1-4.4).

Main product outcome:

Purpose: facilitate the exhibition of Damien Hirst's work of art at The Mori Art Museum in Japan.

Genre: formal speech - negotiations at Narita International Airport.

Mode: text and video.

Style: formal language.

Possible Transfer:

- Mediating, Interpreting and Translating subject specific texts from Spanish & French (L1) into English (L2).
- Giving a public speech in English.
- Debating and formal meetings etiquette and procedures.
- Writing formal texts.

Considering this, Figure 2 depicts the four tasks that will help the teacher to “know what the students know” and will be considered for assessment: each activity should be associated with its rubric which will also be shared with the trainees as a pedagogical tool.

Figure 2

DLE: Preliminary and Main Product Outcomes

Q3. How can I support active knowledge co-construction for my learners?

The third guiding question focuses on the use of methodologies that contribute to co-construction of knowledge by paying attention to social interaction and the use of (digital) media. Table 4 reviews the foundations of the didactic proposal.

Table 4

Designing a Deeper Learning Episode (Q3)

How can I support active knowledge co-construction for my learners?
<p>Construction of Knowledge:</p> <p>(X) inquiry-based learning (X) problem-based learning (X) gamification</p> <p>Social Interaction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Individual and collaborative work. ● Use of L1 and L2. <p>Use of (digital) media:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discussions and meetings will be held digitally via <i>Blackboard Learn</i> (Break out rooms and Open Class Feedback). ● The meeting will be held and recorded on <i>Blackboard Learn</i>.

Q4. How will I support my learners every step of the way?

The role of the educator is completely transformed in this episode, becoming an instigator of creativity and interesting private and open-class discussions in which students can develop critical thinking and work with their peers. The tasks leave room for the student to choose which texts and topics to work on autonomously, completing them one step at a time so that the teacher can monitor the acquisition of content, language, and skills, addressing the problems before it is too late. Table 5 illustrates fundamental aspects in terms of scaffolding, feed-back, feed-up, feed-forward and assessment.

Table 5*Designing a Deeper Learning Episode (Q4)*

How will I support my learners every step of the way?
<p>Scaffolding:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Initial research is scaffolded by providing some texts (written, audio-visual and in different languages: SP/FR/ENG). ● Class and small group discussions will be guided using index cards in which Ss will record their knowledge and conclusions. ● Mediation & Translation tasks will be done in pairs/small groups and monitored by the teacher. ● Examples and instructions will be provided (word count, structure and purpose of each task). ● Role-play. The class will be divided using the jigsaw technique/Aronson's puzzle (group 1: customs officers; group 2; art managers; group 3: cultural and linguistic mediators). Together, they will prepare a draft of the script for the meeting. They will use the resources facilitated by the instructor and other they consider relevant. The drafts will be submitted in advance for the teacher's supervision. <p>Feed-back:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pair feedback during discussions. ● Individual teacher feedback on mediation tasks and meeting script. ● Peer & teacher feedback on role-play and letter. <p>Feed-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Structured worksheets, instructions and assessment grids. <p>Feed-forward:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Individual teacher feedback. ● Peer feedback. ● Self-assessment. <p>Assessment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Learning goals and results made visible for students. ● Skills always present. ● Assessment grids available for each task.

Q5. How will I create and sustain learner engagement?

“Deep practice is a highly focused and reflective activity, it requires deep engagement and long-term commitment and motivation” (Coyle et al., 2023, p. 7). We must not lose sight of the fact that the topics to be covered and the activities proposed must be relevant and motivating so that learning experience is meaningful. In this English class we must add a value to the students' education and connect it, unavoidably, to other subjects and, ultimately, to the professional world.

Table 6

Designing a Deeper Learning Episode (Q5)

How can I support active knowledge co-construction for my learners?
<p>Engagement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Thought provoking topic. ● Professional development. <p>Personal meaningfulness/relevance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Students will become custom officers, art managers & cultural and linguistic mediators. They will all be working with different languages, registers, and texts. And will be involved in various mediating and translating experiences. ● Relevance of the topic as students will be future translators, mediators, and interpreters and will have to deal with cultural differences and various perspectives. ● Development of democratic citizenship: tolerance, acceptance, critical thinking. <p>Opportunities for autonomous learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Independent research on the different definitions and expressions of art. ● Meaningful conversations with peers. ● Individual development of critical thinking and cultural awareness. ● Acting as an expert, making value judgements using formal language. <p>Reflection & Revision:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preparing ideas with justification and examples in order to offer meaningful contributions to the discussions. ● Collecting main arguments of a text within a cultural context and transferring them into another language and context.

Capturing the student's attention is the first step towards meaningful learning, therefore we must be particularly careful as to how we introduce the topic in the classroom. Appendix B, section "01 Basic Understanding" depicts the initial stage or **activation phase**. This stage seeks "to generate learner engagement, activate prior knowledge, establish relevance and set the ground for transfer of learning. Its focus is on facilitating learning by setting clear goals" (Coyle et al., 2023, p. 12). At the beginning of this educational experience, students will identify artistic manifestations by relevant British artists and try to make sense of some of the controversies surrounding the world of art. Prior knowledge is activated with controversial images and a triggering question that will be discussed in small groups.

Each picture comes with a link that redirects the participants to different text modalities (news reports, videos, and podcasts) in different languages (Spanish, language A; English, language B; and French, language C). Students will subsequently be asked to summarise the information in the spaces provided following an example (Appendix B, section "01 Basic Understanding").

When moving on to the next stage, coined the **surface phase** by Coyle, Meyer and Staschen-Dielmann (2023) "learners (will) explore new ideas, facts, concepts and skills to acquire a basic understanding of the content which they demonstrate through a first learning outcome or product. The teacher provides feed-back, feed-up and feed-forward at different levels" (p. 12).

The first learning product was required at the initial stage as preparation for the second task that takes place in this surface phase. After group work and students-students-teacher communication, it is necessary to leave a space for reflection (and some teacher-student interaction) and, as a consequence, an opportunity for autonomous learning is created. The guidelines for each task have been clearly outlined so that students are fully aware of what to do and can work autonomously and independently. Nevertheless, the instructor will always be available to answer questions and monitor the learning process (Appendix B, section "02 Foundational Skills").

The **consolidation phase** focuses on creating opportunities for learners “to deepen their content understanding (to support the process of internalisation) and to deep-practise specific skillsets (to support the process of automatisation)” and future transfer (Coyle et al., 2023, p. 12). Students will be assigned another task to show their understanding and the improvement of their skills in a progressive way. Individual or joint reflection will be fostered, and students’ work will be revised, providing them with specific feedback towards deeper learning (Appendix B, section “03 Deeper Understanding”).

During the final, **transfer phase**, “learners are challenged to apply their knowledge to different contexts and situations. Such application involves utilizing their knowledge and skills through investigating, experimenting, problem solving or decision-making” (Coyle et al., 2023, p. 12). Tables 2 and 3 together with Appendix B, section “04 Deep Practice” and “05 Transfer” illustrate ways in which students will apply and use their newly acquired knowledge and competences in the future.

Figure 3

DLE “Art beyond the Visual”: Structure Overview

4. CONCLUSION

At the beginning of this paper, it was argued that the pluriliteracies framework opens the possibility of a transformation of didactic planning through the promotion of deeper learning guided by a series of fundamental questions which may help educational practitioners shift current systems for the better. The teaching of English as a foreign language (EFL), in particular, can benefit from PTDL by becoming a subject that really fulfils students' needs in different contexts by providing a content of its own.

In order to demonstrate this, we have presented an alternative way of developing a meaningful learning experience – in the form of a Deeper Learning Episode – for a group of undergraduate students in the degree of Translation and Interpreting at an online university in Spain studying the subject English B, which corresponds to a C1 CEFR level.

Due to time constraints, there have only been partial interventions in the group with the material, but the change is already having an impact amongst students, who are now leaving positive comments like these in the end-of-course survey: "*Interesting classes, with varied material and oriented to our Professional future.*" (Student C, translated from Spanish); "[*the teacher*] *Relates the contents with the degree itself, not teaches us English only.*" (Student D, translated from Spanish); "[*the teacher*] *Integrates knowledge into practical part for our future role as translators.*" (Student E, translated from Spanish)

The positive responses have motivated our current and future research focus on the full implementation of these materials and techniques. In conclusion, this preliminary stage has encouraged us to pursue PTDL, potentially renewing language teachers' sense of identity and positively impacting students' learning experiences.

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